

Research Paper

Populace Insight On Development in Public Health Sector of India Subsequent to Functioning Of National Rural Health Mission

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Abstract

National Rural Health Mission implemented in India during 2005-12 whereby Government of India invested almost 90 billion dollars in public health sector over the last seven years. Several claims and counterclaims made related to success and drawbacks and several data put forward in support of both view points. Therefore this survey conducted during April 2011 to September 2011 to evaluate the changes into public health sector as perceived by a common man. The survey found that despite several contradictory and self defeating reports NRHM was successful in establishing people confidence in the public health sector which made lively due to NRHM.

Key words: *National Rural Health Mission; Indian Public Health; People perception*

Introduction:

National Rural Health Mission or NRHM was one of the major interventions by the Government of India since its independence and democratization in the year 1947 to improve the slow moving health indicators of the country (MOHFW, 2005). Successive Common Review Missions or CRMs on NRHM reported that NRHM had succeeded in several parameters and health indicators of the country improved considerable during its implementation from April 2005 to March 2012 (MOHFW G. , 2007,2009, 2010). There numerous data available on the basis of which NRHM could evaluate such sources could identify as *Executive Summary on NRHM* (MOHFW G. , Executive summary December 2010, 2010), it contained work done report on NRHM state wise and group wise also as all states of India divided in four main groups on the recommendations of Empowered Action Group States (MOHFW, Constitution of Empowered Action Group, 2001). Census of Government of India also provided information about decadal growth rate of population, sex ratio, sex ration in the age group 0-6 years (Census, 2001, 2011). Rural Survey (GOI, Rural Health Survey, 2005-12), District Level Households Survey (MOHFW, District level households survey (DLHS), 2004-2010), Sample registration system bulletins (India, 2005-2012) and National Family Health Survey data (IFHS, 2003-2009) were some other sources on which achievements of NRHM could also evaluate. However, speckled data could so confuse and vast that it usually not has any meaning for common people. Common people just looked at the services they received from the public health centre. Therefore this survey conducted to evaluate the people's perception on NRHM and how people of India used to see outcomes of NRHM.

Random survey research was one of the most important areas of measurement in applied social research (Kothari, 2004). The broad area of survey research encompassed any measurement procedures that involved asking questions from respondents where respondents were picked up randomly (Marais, 1990). A random survey differed from a sample survey. Generally, a sample survey

performed with adequate size, confidence level and confidence interval would a most appropriate method for any qualitative research (Mason, 2002, @nd edition). However, conducting a sample survey for NRHM in a country like India has a vast population with large sample size considered expensive and exhaustive. However, a random survey could also indicate some key issues or at least it found to be sufficient to judge some questions and validate certain hypothesis.

A sample survey used to be more expensive but the most reliable form of research provided it is implemented and executed resourcefully. Design of questionnaire, size of the sample and methods of data collection requires great skill and level of intelligence. In this case, a survey conducted with the help of cautiously designed paper based questionnaire. The data received then put into computer software namely '*Survey System 10*' and the results analyzed in the form of *Chart* and *Tables*.

Methods

Survey sampling:

For collecting data on a large group of people (called a "population"), I wanted to minimize the impact that the survey would have on me. It has been often not necessary to survey the entire population. Instead, a random sample of people from the population considered sufficient evidence. Conclusions drawn based on random survey and this exactly happened in this case as certain results discarded based on random survey. For conducting a random survey, the questionnaire spread to different respondents through the mode of volunteers. In this case, the total population or universe was the total population of the country in the age group 18 and above.

Sample size calculator

The sample size calculated by using a sample size calculator presented as a public service of Creative Research Systems survey software. The choices entered in a calculator to find the sample size. Ultimately, the random survey conducted in states of India namely Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Haryana, Himachal,

Jharkhand, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Orissa, Punjab, Rajasthan, and West Bengal. The random survey was involved with 1687 persons. Those persons were heterogeneous in terms of state of domicile, caste, community, gender, age, and landscape. 1050 individuals replied the questions specially designed for this purpose. Out of 1050 responses, 722 responses were recordable and perusable. The questions designed in such a manner that their answer might enable some logical findings. The answers of 722 responses analyzed among different variables.

Results:

In *Table- 1* you may please see the category of people surveyed. People were categorized in two categories such as *Above poverty line (APL)* and *Below poverty line (BPL)*. This was done because several schemes were implemented under NRHM for *BPL* category only. Almost 21 percent of the total surveyed population belonged to *APL* category while remaining 79 percent belonged to *BPL* category, which significant.

In *Table -2* you may please see the place of residence of the respondents mentioned. It would become clear from *Table 2* that almost 47 percent respondent belonged to rural areas and thirty two percent belonged to hilly or hard to reach or tribal areas. Almost 21 percent respondents lived in any urban areas such as Metro Cities, State or District head quarters. The higher number of respondent living in rural, tribal, hilly or hard to reach areas could most significant.

Table-3 would say about the how many times respondent or family in general visited any public health centre during last seven years. It said that approximately 11 percent, 53 percent, 26 percent visited any public health centre almost 1 to 5 times, 10 to 15 times and more than 15 times respectively over the last seven years. Thus a total of almost 80 percent of surveyed population visited any public health centre at least one times during the last seven years and this result most significant. However, 11 percent of surveyed population said that they never visited any public health centre at all over the last seven years.

Almost 79 percent said that they noticed improvements in health facilities in last seven years, however 21 percent also said in negative.

37 percent felt very satisfied with improvements in the last seven years while 58 percent felt little satisfied among. 5 percent said that they so disappointing with public health centres in the country.

OPD and Immunization were the services most accessed by the surveyed population which fell around 33 percent and 61 percent respectively. However IPD and Diagnostics services availed by almost 6 percent population.

But the difference between the choice of public health sector and private health sector evident as more than seventy four percent said that they prefer public health centre, which most significant and surprised all of us.

74 percent population said that corruption in the system prevalent and termed as key problem, while 16 percent complained about poor infrastructure and 5 percent complained about lack of public amenities and further 5 percent complained about lack of adequate care at public health facilities. 79 percent of the surveyed population were male while twenty one percent were female.

Conclusion:

The survey revealed that National Rural Health Mission made its inroads across the country. High focussed states performed better however corruption cases surfaced from Uttar Pradesh, Jharkhand and Chhattisgarh casted doubts over people mind. Though the public health sectors become lively yet it required people confidence and diminish vulnerabilities.

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Vitae:

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Tables:

Table 1: Select the category you belong...

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
APL	152 21%	152 100%	0 0%
BPL	570 79%	0 0%	570 100%

Table 2: You reside in.....

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
Rural area	342 47%	0 0%	342 60%
Urban area	38 5%	38 25%	0 0%
Metro City	38 5%	38 25%	0 0%
District Hq.	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
State Hq.	76 11%	76 50%	0 0%
Hilly area	228 32%	0 0%	228 40%

Table 3: How many times you or family in general visited any public health centre during last seven years?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
1-5	76 11%	76 50%	0 0%
5-10	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
10-15	380 53%	0 0%	380 67%
More than 15	190 26%	0 0%	190 33%
Never	76 11%	76 50%	0 0%

Table 4: Do you notice improvements in health facilities in last seven years?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
Yes	570 79%	0 0%	570 100%
No	152 21%	152 100%	0 0%

Table 5: How much you feel satisfied with improvements?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
Very satisfied	266 37%	0 0%	266 47%
Little satisfied	418	114	304

	58%	75%	53%
		27%	73%
Unsatisfied	0	0	0
	0%	0%	0%
	0%	0%	0%
Very disappointing	38	38	0
	5%	25%	0%
		100%	0%

Table 6: Which service most reliable?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	684	114	570
OPD	228	38	190
	33%	33%	33%
		17%	83%
IPD	0	0	0
	0%	0%	0%
	0%	0%	0%
Immunization	418	76	342
	61%	67%	60%
		18%	82%
Ambulance	0	0	0
	0%	0%	0%
	0%	0%	0%
JSY	0	0	0
	0%	0%	0%
	0%	0%	0%
Free medicines	0	0	0
	0%	0%	0%
	0%	0%	0%
Diagnostics	38	0	38
	6%	0%	7%
		0%	100%

Table 7: Do you prefer private sector more than public health sector?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
Yes	190	152	38
	26%	100%	7%
		80%	20%
No	532	0	532
	74%	0%	93%
		0%	100%

Table 8: What are main weaknesses in public health sector according to you?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
Corruption	532	76	456
	74%	50%	80%
		14%	86%
Infrastructure	114	0	114
	16%	0%	20%
		0%	100%
Public amenities	38	38	0
	5%	25%	0%
		100%	0%
Doctors	0	0	0
	0%	0%	0%
	0%	0%	0%
Paramedics	0	0	0
	0%	0%	0%
	0%	0%	0%
Medicines	0	0	0
	0%	0%	0%
	0%	0%	0%
Adequate care	38	38	0
	5%	25%	0%
		100%	0%

Table 9: Are you a male of female?

	Total	Select the category you belong...	
		APL	BPL
Base	722	152	570
Male	570	152	418
	79%	100%	73%
		27%	73%
Female	152	0	152
	21%	0%	27%
		0%	100%

Table 10: Dropout Analysis

Quit Percentage Base: All Questionnaires

S. No	Question	Ans	% age	Change	Quit
1	Select the category you belong...	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%

2	You reside in.....	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%
3	How many times you or family in general visited any	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%
4	Do you notice improvements in health facilities in last seven years?	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%
5	How much you feel satisfied with improvements?	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%
6	Which service most reliable?	684	95%	-5.3%	0.0%
7	Do you prefer private sector more than public health sector?	722	100%	5.3%	0.0%
8	What are main weaknesses in public health sector according to you?	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%
9	Are you a male of female?	722	100%	0.0%	0.0%

9. Charts:

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